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Abstract	This document presents the development and implementation of a comprehensive data model and sensor system. The data model facilitates the transformation of raw sensor data into a format usable by the geomodel, employing Kafka as the data broker for real-time data handling. The process includes sensor calibration, data transformation, additional calculations for integration with Leapfrog Geo software, and the

generation of synthetic datasets for geomodelling, culminating in the visualization of data in the geomodel. The sensor techniques include Measurement While Drilling (MWD) for real-time data on rock properties, a multispectral camera for mineralogy and composition analysis, Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) for chemical analysis of drilling fluids, ultrasonic testing for mechanical properties of rocks, and Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) for imaging subsurface resistivity variations. Each sensor's data is processed, calibrated, and integrated into the data model using Kafka, ensuring accurate and reliable geological data.

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Executive summary

This document constitutes the deliverable of D2.4, “Real-time rock characterization as input to systems for sustainable underground mining” for the Horizon Europe project titled “Autonomous Exploration and Extraction of Deep Mineral Deposits” (acronym: PERSEPHONE; Grant Agreement no: 101138451). It is based on the conditions outlined in the Grant Agreement and its annexes, as signed by the European Commission.

Task 2.4 focuses on developing and simulating a data handling model that enables the transformation of raw sensor outputs (developed in WP6) into actionable geological information for use in the geo-modelling tools of WP7. Given that the core sensor and modelling developments are addressed in separate work packages, Task 2.4 centres on designing the integration framework to link sensor data to geological modelling platforms.

A simulated data pipeline was designed and tested using Kafka as a central data broker for real-time streaming. Sensor data is collected at the mining face and transmitted through edge computing units where it is filtered, calibrated, and transformed into standardized data formats. The architecture emphasizes vendor-agnostic integration using open APIs, allowing platforms such as Leapfrog Geo and MineRP system to subscribe to and process the sensor data. This system was tested using fictitious data to validate end-to-end connectivity and was further demonstrated in a virtual simulation wherein sensor-derived values dynamically update a geological block model.

Five sensor suites developed in WP6 are central to this workflow:

- MWD (Measurement While Drilling): captures real-time drilling parameters such as penetration rate and feed pressure to infer rock hardness and structure. An indentation tool was developed as a calibration mechanism to support conversion into quantitative hardness metrics.
- Multispectral camera: captures reflected light across specific wavelengths to infer mineralogical composition, serving as a proxy for grade and lithological boundaries.

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- LIBS (Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy): ablate material using laser pulses to obtain elemental compositions, directly supporting ore grade estimation.
- Acoustics: utilises ultrasonic waves to determine P-wave velocity, offering indirect indicators of rock integrity and mechanical strength.
- ERT (Electrical Resistivity Tomography): applies current through electrodes to measure subsurface resistivity, providing spatial models of lithological and mineralogical contrast (e.g. conductive sulfides).

The designed workflow progresses through seven core steps; sensor calibration, data transformation, attribute computation, data integration and visualization.

The work carried out in Task 2.4 lays the foundation for a robust real-time rock characterization framework. The capabilities and requirements of several promising sensor technologies were reviewed, and a data integration strategy was developed that can incorporate the corresponding outputs into a geomodel. Despite the challenges of incomplete sensor maturity, by using simulated and fictitious data a work-flow solution was developed to demonstrate end-to-end data integration capability. The simulation illustrates the capability of the system to support dynamic geological modelling, contributing toward the broader PERSEPHONE objective of an autonomous, continuously learning mining system.

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1 Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
API	Application Programming Interface
CUP	KGHM Cuprum
DX.X	DX.X Deliverable Number
EPI	Epiroc
ERT	Electrical Resistivity Tomography
GSB	Geological Survey of Belgium
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IP	Induced Polarization
KPI	KPI Key Performance Indicator
LIBS	Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy
LTU	Luleå Technical University
MRP	MineRP
MWD	Measure While Drilling
OK	Ordinary Kriging
RBF	Radial Basis Function
RCS	Rig Control System
SPE	Spectral Industries (Netherlands)
SWIR	Short-Wave Infrared (wavelength range ~900–1700 nm)
UCS	Uniaxial Compressive Strength
V_p	Primary (P-wave) velocity,
WP	Work Package

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope of the document

The work within this specific task T2.4 and related deliverable D2.4 is focused on the retrieval of detailed information about the ore body content as an important part of the rock excavation and drilling process. The report details the work performed regarding sensor technologies and data flows and simulation models for geological overview.

According to the task description the objectives and work to be performed within the specific task is divided in different steps for easy overview as stated below:

1. *Detailed specifications for the data retrieval system are generated, highlighting the need for the level of detail of the ore grade and the stage in the mining process at which this information is required to increase sustainability.*
2. *The specification is used to evaluate, review, and test innovative sensors for rock and structural characterization, which have the potential to generate data at the specified level of detail and at the correct stage in the excavation process. This part involves a feasibility study for the integration of site-specific real-time rock characterization data from the drill machine with data from stand-alone measurement systems.*
3. *A proof of concept to be generated where the retrieved ore grade information is linked to a geomodel of the orebody, which is thereafter updated according to the methods to be developed in WP6.*

This deliverable document is structured to cover all the above. It provides background context for the task, describes the data model development methodology, details the results of the step-by-step integration (with illustrative cases for each sensor), and draws conclusions about system performance and future work. The document also includes a comprehensive Annex with technical details on each sensor's testing, data processing, calibration, and integration. By combining the narrative of the main report and the detailed annexes, the document serves as both a summary for stakeholders and a technical reference for implementation.

2.2 Background

Deliverable D2.4 is formally defined as the "Review, testing and evaluation of sensing techniques for online rock characterization in simulated environments." In line with this, the work completed recognizes that by mid-project (Month 18) the sensor prototypes developed in WP6 are not fully operational due to the delivery of WP6 planned in M22. Task 2.4 focuses on developing the linking framework and performing simulation-based evaluations rather than field demonstrations, that will be a part of Task 3.2. Essentially, Task 2.4 has functioned

as a bridge between WP6 (sensor development, deliverable at M22) and WP7 (geo-model and data platform development). An additional aspect of rock characterization data generation developed within Task 2.4 itself is in the area of MWD hardness calibration. A novel indentation device was built and tested to provide an absolute measure of rock hardness, which can calibrate the relative MWD data (which in current practice yields only a qualitative indication of hardness). All other sensor data utilized in this task were drawn from WP6's ongoing developments or knowledge base (for example, ore grades from lab tests or known signatures from literature) or they were generated synthetically to stand in for real measurements.

A summary of the sensor's description (more details on the decision process in D1.2) and the rock properties they measure, as well as how those properties relate to the geological model is listed in the bullets below. Figure 1 shows an Epiroc drill rig and describes at what stage in the drilling process the different sensors are used. This sampling strategy is also applicable for future mining machines to be developed in the related task 2.2 (Hole deviation monitoring systems for long hole drilling).

Figure 1: Sampling strategies for the different sensor technologies.

LIBS (Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy) (SPE)

- *Description:* uses a high-powered laser to ablate a small part of the sample and analyze the emitted light spectrum to identify elemental composition.
- *Measured property:* elemental composition (multielement assay of rock powder in slurry form)
- *Geomodel attribute:* directly provides ore grade information (e.g. % of target metals) and clues to mineralogy
- *Limitations:* requires careful calibration for quantitative accuracy; safety measures for high-power laser; performance can be affected by particle size and slurry homogeneity.
- *Sampling strategy:* during drilling.

Multispectral Camera (GSB)

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- *Description:* captures image data at specific frequencies across the electromagnetic spectrum.
- *Measured property:* mineralogy and material composition via spectral reflectance (approx. 350–2500 nm range)
- *Geomodel attribute:* directly estimates potential grade; indirectly indicates mineralogy/lithology.
- *Limitations:* dependent on lighting conditions, requires calibration, requires direct exposure to the target surface for accurate readings.
- *Sampling strategy:* before drilling

Electrical/Electromagnetic Methods (ERT/IP) (GSB)

- *Description:* employs electrical and magnetic fields to determine the subsurface geological structure and rock properties.
- *Measured property:* rock mechanical properties (resistivity, conductivity, induced polarization)
- *Geomodel attribute:* indirect indicator of rock type boundaries and can highlight structures or mineralized zones
- *Limitations:* depth penetration may be limited; influenced by adjacent strata and requires interpretation.
- *Sampling strategy:* before drilling

Acoustic (GSB)

- *Description:* uses sound waves to measure physical properties such as density and porosity indirectly.
- *Measured property:* mechanical wave velocity through rock (p-wave velocity), linked to elasticity, density, and fracturing
- *Geomodel attribute:* indicates rock competence and fracturing (indirectly structure)
- *Limitations:* requires coupling with rock, affected by noise and drilling vibrations.
- *Sampling strategy:* downhole logging while drilling or post-drilling analysis.

MWD (Measurement While Drilling) Real-Time Rock Characterization (EPI, LTU)

- *Description:* measures rock properties in real-time using the response of drilling mechanics.
- *Measured property:* drilling parameters (pressure, speed, etc.)
- *Geomodel attribute:* indicates changes in rock hardness and presence of weak zones or voids (which can be correlated to rock type or structure)
- *Limitations:* indirect measure, correlation with actual rock properties needed; influenced by drill bit wear and drilling conditions.
- *Sampling Strategy:* during drilling

On-Site Hardness Measurement Tool (EPI, CUP)

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- *Description:* rig mounted device used on-site to measure the hardness of exposed rock faces.
- *Measured Property:* hardness
- *Geomodel attribute:* directly indicates hardness.
- *Limitations:* limited to exposed surfaces; may not represent bulk material.
- *Sampling strategy:* before drilling

2.3 Related documents

This report should be read in conjunction with the following project documents and deliverables, which provide background and complementary information:

- D1.1 - Literature survey on SOA technologies and existing roadmaps in the mining industry.
- D1.2 - Requirements, specifications and benchmarking tools for proposed technologies.
- D6.1 - Design and validation of sensors to assess the composition of the orebody (chemical). This document will detail the construction and testing of the actual sensor prototypes (the LIBS instrument, multispectral imager, etc.) and provide data that will eventually replace the simulated inputs used here.
- D6.2 - Design and validation of methods of analysis of structural properties of the orebody. This document will detail the construction and testing of the actual sensor prototypes (ERT, acoustic, etc.) and provide data that will eventually replace the simulated inputs used here.

3 Data model development

This section describes the development of the data model and integration framework that connects raw sensor outputs to the geological model. The term “data model” here refers not to a database schema, but to the structured pathway and transformations that the sensor data undergo a route to becoming part of the geomodel (the digital twin of the orebody).

Each of the selected sensors produces RAW data of varying type and size. For instance, the LIBS produces spectral data (potentially thousands of intensity values per shot), the multispectral camera produces images, and MWD produces time-series of drilling parameters. Handling this variety requires carefully mapping out, how to standardize and combine the data. Key questions addressed were: *How should rock characteristics (composition, hardness, etc.) be extracted or derived from each sensor’s raw data? What data types and formats are appropriate for storing/transmitting these characteristics? What filtering or preprocessing is needed to ensure data quality?*

Due to WP6 delivery is not until M22 all sensors cannot deliver real data for this task, our development used simulated data in most cases. This allowed us to proceed with building the integration pipeline and testing the data flow even in the absence of final sensor hardware.

3.1 Methodology

The data model and integration workflow were developed through an iterative and collaborative methodology. The task 2.4 team (LTU, EPI, GSB, SPE, MRP) met regularly to define the interfaces and steps needed. Meanwhile, WP7 was developing the geomodels, setting up the central data broker and initial MineRP platform connections, which we aligned with.

A guiding decision was to use Leapfrog Geo for the modelling environment in this phase (responsible LTU). Since obtaining an immediately “dynamic” geomodel with custom code was beyond scope in the time frame, Leapfrog’s implicit modelling and automation features served as a proxy for a future integrated system. Essentially, Leapfrog was set up on a data server to watch a data source and to refresh the model when new data arrived. This mimicked an automatic model update pipeline.

Facilitating an end-to-end data integration solution between sensor technologies and other mine technical systems, Kafka was chosen as the data broker technology (responsible MRP). Kafka handles high frequency data streams, allowing multiple consumers to access the streams in real time.

To map out the processing steps, we used a flowchart (Figure 1) that corresponds to the Steps 0–7 described below.

- Step 0 (Sensor calibration): each sensor is calibrated to identify relevant geotechnical and geochemical signals. This step involves setting up the sensors to recognize specific characteristics and properties of the rock.
- Steps 1-2 (Data transformation): raw data is processed into readable, normalized formats that can be used for downstream the data handling process.
- Steps 3-4 (Attribute computation): external algorithms compute geological attributes not natively handled by Leapfrog Geo (e.g. UCS derivation). This module can be developed further to mitigate dependencies on specific software suppliers.
- Steps 5-6 (Data integration): processed sensor data is mapped to geological parameters and streamed to modelling platforms for implicit block model construction and real-time data integration.
- Step 7 (Visualization in the geomodel): Leapfrog Geo is used to render an evolving virtual orebody based on simulated or real-time sensor inputs.

Each step was further elaborated and assigned to responsible partners. For example, EPI, GSB and SPE focused on sensors data handling (Steps 0–2 and calibration aspects), while LTU and MRP worked on the portions involving the data stream pipeline and broker system, synthetic data generation, Leapfrog modeling (Steps 3–7).

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the data handling model developed in Task 2.4. This model is a generic model and can be adapted and used in other WP-s.

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4 Results

For clarity, this section will present the data handling process in two parts: first, a per-sensor perspective on how raw data becomes usable information (Steps 0–2 for each sensor), and second, the integrated modelling perspective (Steps 3–7 encompassing data fusion, modelling, and output).

4.1 Sensor data handling (Steps 0-2)

In this section, we outline how each selected sensor's data is collected (Step 1) and processed into a readable, standardized format (Step 2), including any calibration (Step 0) that was applied. Each sensor has unique data characteristics, so these steps were tailored accordingly. A quick reference of the data types and processing for each sensor is listed below:

- **MWD:** time-series drilling data (pressures, rates) → filter noise, compute derived metrics → output file (XML/CSV) log per hole interval.
- **Indentation device (MWD Calibration):** individual hardness measurements (force vs penetration curve) → derive UCS estimate via calibration curve → output absolute hardness value.
- **Multispectral Camera:** SWIR image frames → radiometric calibration, image segmentation → output JSON file with classified mineral map.
- **LIBS slurry analyser:** laser spectra sequence → spectral pretreatment (baseline, peak detection) → output JSON file elemental concentrations per depth interval.
- **Acoustic (Ultrasonic):** ultrasonic waveform → pick P-wave arrival, calculate velocity → output JSON file with V_p value with metadata.
- **ERT:** voltage readings across electrodes → quality filtering, inversion preprocessing → output JSON file with apparent resistivity values with coordinates.

Common to all sensors, as noted, is the transmission of results to Kafka in a structured form, which marks the end of Step 2 for each. It is essential that all sensor data sent to Kafka include timestamps to ensure synchronization both among the sensor data and with the localization data derived from the results in WP4. Below we describe each sensor's process. Please refer to Chapter 7 Annex for a more detailed description of each sensor.

4.1.1 MWD (Measure While Drilling)

4.1.1.1 Data acquisition

During drilling operations, the Measure While Drilling (MWD) system collects real-time operational data through sensors integrated into the drill rig. These sensors continuously monitor key drilling parameters—such as feed pressure, rotation pressure and water pressure (see Table 1)—which are transmitted to the

Rig Control System (RCS) to support performance optimization and early detection of drilling issues.

Table 1: Examples of MWD parameters from an Epiroc drill rig

Parameter	Unit
Penetration rate	m/min
Rotation pressure	bar
Water flow	0/1
Water pressure	Bar
Feed pressure	bar
Percussion pressure	Bar
Dampening pressure	Bar
Time tag	YYYY h:m:s

In addition to pressure and load data, the system also records drill string position and depth using onboard length sensors. These are used to calculate the penetration rate, the rate at which the drill advances into the rock. While most pressure parameters are operator-controlled inputs, the penetration rate is an observable output that reflects how efficiently the applied forces translate into drilling progress.

By analysing the interaction between input forces (e.g., feed and rotation pressure) and output response (e.g., penetration rate), MWD data provides valuable insight into the mechanical response of the rock mass. Slower penetration under constant load often indicates higher rock strength or the presence of harder formations, making MWD a practical indirect tool for assessing rock hardness and drilling conditions in real time.

4.1.1.2 Data processing and calibration

MWD data on its own provides a relative indication of rock hardness, for example, slower penetration (all else equal) implies harder rock. However, numerous factors can skew this: operator settings, bit wear, changes in drilling mode, or the initial collaring of the hole (where lower pressures are used). To extract meaningful rock characterization, the MWD data must be normalized and calibrated. There is a need of filtering algorithms or methods to remove obvious anomalies (such as pauses in drilling or rod changes) and focused on steady drilling sections. To get absolute rock strength (like UCS in MPa), one cannot rely on MWD alone. That is why a calibration tool was introduced: the indentation device.

The indentation device, when used on the rock face, provides an independent measure of hardness by pressing a spherical indenter into the rock and recording the force-displacement curve. This device was tested on various rocks (from very

hard to soft) and was shown to produce characteristic force-penetration curves that differ by rock type. The initial portion of the curve (up to the yield point) can be used to back-calculate an equivalent UCS. By doing indentations on the face near where the drill is starting, we obtain a UCS estimate for that specific rock. We then use that to calibrate the MWD penetration rate readings. Essentially, if the MWD system says “hardness X” (a relative number) for a certain penetration rate, and the indentation yields UCS = 150 MPa, we can assign that absolute value to the MWD reading at that location. Subsequent MWD readings in similar conditions can be translated into MPa by this calibration curve. The development and testing of the indentation device are explained more in detail in the annex chapter 7.1.

In practice, there will be a need to perform several indentations across the face (to account for variability). These values are averaged and used to adjust the hardness scale in the drill’s software (or in a post-processing script). One existing software, Underground Manager (Epiroc), currently displays MWD-derived hardness on a user-defined relative scale (color-coded from soft to hard). With our approach, a software (or a similar system) could incorporate the indentation results to shift from a relative scale to an absolute UCS scale (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Underground Manager (Epiroc) showing MWD values and how it could look with value of calibrated hardness presented instead of relative hardness.

4.1.1.3 Data transmission

Once the MWD data for a round is processed and (if applicable) calibrated with indentation input, the results are packaged containing fields such as time stamp, drillhole ID, depth intervals, average penetration rate, estimated UCS, etc. This is then sent to Kafka, specifically to the “MWD” topic, for integration downstream.

4.1.2 LIBS slurry

4.1.2.1 Data acquisition

The acronym LIBS is short for Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy. LIBS works by vaporizing a minute amount of material with a high-energy laser pulse, generating a plasma that emits light characteristic of the sample’s elemental

composition. While LIBS provides semi-quantitative data by default, accurate quantification requires system-specific calibration to account for environmental and instrumental variables. In the PERSEPHONE project, a customized LIBS system is being developed for integration directly on a production drill rig to enable in-situ chemical profiling during drilling. Although still in early development, the system aims to continuously analyze drilling fluids through a dedicated slurry collection unit, providing geochemical data that supports real-time mine modelling. However, it is already known that an operating drill rig is a challenging environment for a fundamentally delicate optical system such as a LIBS sensor. Particularly vibrations and shock loads while driving and drilling can be enormous on the LIBS system.

LIBS sensors are capable of generating large volumes of data in short timeframes. Each LIBS measurement produces a spectrum, which is essentially a reading from the linear sensor array of the spectrometer. A typical dataset consists of many such measurements collected over a given interval (e.g., one minute of continuous operation), resulting in a large matrix of spectral data. This raw data, while abstract to the untrained observer, contains valuable information about the chemical composition of the sample. It must be properly managed and processed to extract concentrations of target elements relevant to geological modelling.

A typical LIBS dataset comprises several key components (illustrated in Figure 4):

- *Intensity matrix*: a 2D array where each row corresponds to a full spectrum (i.e., one measurement) and each column maps to a specific spectrometer pixel.
- *Wavelength vector*: a list indicating the wavelength (in nm) associated with each pixel in the intensity matrix.
- *Saturation matrix*: a Boolean matrix of the same shape as the intensity matrix, flagging whether each intensity reading is saturated and should be excluded from further analysis.
- *Timestamp metadata*: a time vector recording when each spectrum was captured, allowing synchronization with other data sources in the digital twin architecture.

These components together form the primary input to the data processing pipeline, which translates raw optical spectra into meaningful geochemical indicators for downstream integration and visualization.

Figure 4: Typical structure of a LIBS dataset.

Data processing and calibration

Processing LIBS data is inherently complex and highly site-specific. It requires expert understanding of both the sensor and its environment, as there is no universal pipeline for turning raw spectra into usable information. In general, the process is divided into three stages (illustrated in Figure 5). First, the vast data generated often gigabytes per minute is reduced and filtered onboard the sensor to ease transfer and storage. The second section mostly does the computational heavy lifting. These steps prepare and reformat the LIBS data again into smaller parameters. These parameters are the extracted parts of the data that have direct correlation with the information of interest, generally the composition of some sample or in this case, drilling fluids. These are passed to a calibration model, a predefined algorithm trained on known samples, which converts the spectral patterns into meaningful concentrations.

Figure 5: High-level overview of a LIBS data processing pipeline.

4.1.2.2 Data calibration

The calibration phase of a LIBS sensor works as follows. First a set of samples will need to be collected that is representative for the material that will be worked with during operation. This set of samples needs to comply with a couple of requirements. Most importantly, it needs to be representative for all materials that might be encountered during real operation. The predictions of any sensor might be compromised if they are made on material that was not included in the calibration dataset.

After a calibration set has been collected, the samples need to be analysed by the LIBS sensor and by another reference analytical technique. This is another critical step in which it is very important that the LIBS measurements are taken in an environment that is similar to the environment in which the application takes place. This is often not possible for reference techniques that are almost exclusively lab-based. That is where it is extremely important to evaluate all potential sampling errors between LIBS and the reference. In SPE's experience lab-based reference measurements have excellent analytical accuracy and precision, but almost always have large sampling issues. These errors will be reflected in the LIBS calibration model. See Figure 6 for a simplified overview of how this process works.

Figure 6: Simplified overview how a calibration model is created and what it does.

4.1.2.3 Data transmission

Once the LIBS system processes the slurry data and applies the calibration model, the resulting information such as copper percentage or other elemental grades is packaged as structured JSON records. Each record includes a timestamp, spatial location, and geochemical metrics, and is sent via the Kafka platform under a dedicated LIBS topic.

4.1.3 Multispectral camera

4.1.3.1 Data acquisition

The aim of the multispectral camera is to capture and process a multispectral image of the rock face in a few seconds, to produce a reference image to help decision-making for further exploration. The device is based on one or more imaging cameras equipped with motorized filters to capture image data at specific wavelengths across the electromagnetic spectrum (from UV to infrared, depending on the type of mineralization/host rock/exploration objective). These images are then processed to infer the mineralogy/composition based on a machine learning (ML) model trained on reference datasets (use case specific wavelengths and model). The output product is a reference classified image of the rock face.

The method is based on UV to SWIR reflectance/fluorescence imagery, built-in a compact and resilient format with decent illumination power to be operated at a few meters of the rock face. The technologies used will be built upon a compact scientific imaging device developed previously by GSB-RBINS, relying on the

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recent industry developments in compact InGaAs sensors for the SWIR range, and high-power high-efficiency UV-VIS LED technologies for the fluorescence imaging.

The technology will rely on two physical phenomena that allow to detect of specific mineral species with their optical properties: the absorption of specific wavelengths in the visible to near-infrared range (900 - 1700nm) and the fluorescence emission when exposed to UV light (275 and 365nm).

Figure 7: SWIR multispectral camera deployed in Persephone abandoned mine case study.

4.1.3.2 Data processing and calibration

For the case studies considered in Persephone, multispectral images are taken along the mine face with a short-wave infrared (SWIR) camera (900–1700 nm), capturing up to 8 reflectance images in predefined spectral regions (defined according to local mineralization's and mine requirements) (Figure 7). An on-board processing computer processes the image using 1) pre-recorded reflectance calibration, as it is impractical to place calibration target everywhere in the mine) and 2) a pre-trained segmentation/indexation algorithm tailored for the particular use case, using reference samples from each case study.

4.1.3.3 Data transmission

Each image processing result is tagged with the current timestamp (in sync with the robotic platform time). Processed results (mineral IDs, purity or Cu% estimates, etc.) are serialized as JSON and sent to the Kafka data broker. These

workflows are also valid in the case of multispectral cameras working in the UV-VNIR range. Figure 8 illustrates the workflow for the two case studies for the project (i.e., GM abandoned mine and KGHM deep mine). Please refer to Annex for a more detailed description of the data transformation method.

Figure 8: Multispectral processing workflows for the two Persephone case studies.

In the abandoned mine case study (GM), the SWIR camera captures reflectance images of the rock face in the 900–1700 nm range to identify magnesite and distinguish it from gangue minerals like silica, dunitite, and serpentinite. Images are calibrated, filtered, and assembled into spectral cubes. A machine learning classifier (e.g., random forest) then labels pixels as “magnesite” or not. The system groups connected pixels into chunks and calculates their purity, assigning each to a predefined category (e.g., Group 1 = >99% MgCO₃). The results, including timestamp and spatial stats, are serialized as JSON and streamed via Kafka.

In the KGHM deep mine case study, the SWIR system estimates copper content in dolomite layers. After standard calibration, reference samples are collected and paired with lab-measured Cu% values to train a regression model (e.g., PLSR or random forest). The model is applied to new image data to predict Cu% per pixel or region. Results, including mean and max copper values, are output in JSON format for integration.

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To manage bandwidth and system robustness, raw spectral data remain on the edge computer internal drive for about a week in a circular buffer, giving engineers enough time to re-run or troubleshoot a scan without flooding the mine network. Only the compact JSON results travel over the network. For long-term needs, a summary package can be manually download from the camera—comprising the classified mineral image and its metadata—into an archive file system, where it can be retained for years and serve geological modelling and dashboarding without occupying expensive local storage.

4.1.4 Acoustic

4.1.4.1 Data acquisition

Ultrasonic testing is a widely adopted non-destructive technique for evaluating the mechanical properties of rocks. It is a well-established non-destructive evaluation technique, which involves transmitting high-frequency sound waves (typically above 20 kHz) through a material and analysing the wave's travel time, velocity, attenuation, and reflection behaviour to infer material characteristics.

In geological and geotechnical contexts, ultrasonic tests are used to measure P-wave (primary or compressional wave) velocity, which directly correlates with key mechanical and physical properties of rock materials, including elastic moduli, porosity and density, anisotropy and heterogeneity, fracture detection, weathering and damage assessment.

To acquire these measurements, the project utilizes the Proceq Pundit Lab+ system paired with three transducer sets (54 kHz standard, 250 kHz standard, and 54 kHz exponential) suited to different conditions. The transducers are configured in one of three arrangements (Figure 9):

- *Direct transmission (preferred in lab)*: signal travels directly across the sample.
- *Semi-direct*: for constrained geometries.
- *Indirect/surface*: used in field tests where only one surface is accessible.

Transducers are connected to the device using coaxial cables of variable lengths depending on setup (shorter for lab, longer for field). Regular calibration using reference materials with known velocities is performed to maintain measurement accuracy. Environmental factors such as temperature and humidity are carefully controlled to minimize measurement variability. More details on the equipment can be found in D6.2

Figure 9: Transducer arrangement categories.

4.1.4.2 Data calibration

To ensure accurate and consistent measurements, the ultrasonic equipment is calibrated using two reference rods with known *Time of Flight* (TOF) values. TOF represents the time taken for an ultrasonic wave to travel from the emitting transducer at one end of the rod to the receiving transducer at the other end. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the first calibration rod with a TOF of 25.4 ms and the second one with a TOF of 100.4 ms. Additionally, a specialized third rod –also with a TOF of 25.4 ms –is provided. Unlike the first two, this rod includes dedicated cavities designed to accommodate the shape of exponential transducers. This allows for calibration in configurations that replicate real measurement conditions when exponential transducers are used, ensuring accurate alignment and effective signal coupling.

Figure 10: Exponential transducers.

The known travel time allows us to determine the *P-wave velocity* (or longitudinal wave velocity) of the calibration material, which is a key parameter in ultrasonic testing. The first has a TOF of 25.4 ms and a physical length of 69.4 mm. The P-wave velocity equals to 2732 m/s. A very similar value is obtained for the second rod.

The P-wave velocities obtained from the calibration rods—approximately 2732 to 2739 m/s—are comparable to those typically found in low-velocity rocks such as shales. However, these values are significantly lower, by a factor of about 2 to 2.6, than those observed in denser, more massive rocks like certain magmatic bodies, quartzite, or limestone, where P-wave velocities can exceed 6000 m/s. To ensure reliable calibration across a broader range of geological materials, rock samples with higher P-wave velocities, such as limestone and quartzite, are also used as calibration standards. These materials provide appropriate benchmarks when working with high-velocity rock types, enhancing the accuracy of ultrasonic measurements in diverse lithological contexts.

4.1.4.3 Data transmission

In the current and future setup, where ultrasonic sensors are integrated into the robotic systems for in-situ geological exploration, it is crucial to ensure that the generated P-wave velocity (V_p) data is transmitted and stored efficiently. Kafka

(**Error! Reference source not found.**1) serves as the backbone for streaming this data from the sensors to the database in near real-time. Once a measurement is completed, whether in a lab or directly in the field, the sensor system outputs the computed Vp-value along with contextual metadata such as test arrangement, path length, and test environment. Kafka ingests these data packets and streams them to downstream services where they are parsed, validated, and inserted into the Measurements table (further details on the measurements, site, sample and equipment table can be found in the Annex).

Figure 11: Relationship between ultrasonic sensor test and the ultrasonic database through Kafka.

This architecture enables scalable, robust tracking of dynamic measurement data. Field deployment of ultrasonic sensors presents several challenges compared to controlled laboratory conditions. Irregular rock geometries, material heterogeneity, moisture, and environmental noise can distort wave propagation and reduce signal quality. In the field, indirect sensor configurations are often necessary, which complicates wave behaviour and makes velocity estimates less reliable. Addressing these issues requires careful calibration, adaptive data processing, and a stepwise validation approach that begins with simple field sites and gradually expands to more complex geological settings. This strategy helps ensure accurate, scalable, and traceable in-situ measurements.

4.1.5 ERT

4.1.5.1 Data acquisition

Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) is a geophysical technique used in mineral exploration to image subsurface resistivity variations, which can indicate the presence of ore bodies, alteration zones, and structural controls on mineralization. The method works by injecting electrical current into the ground through electrodes and measuring the resulting potential differences, which are then inverted to produce 2D or 3D models of subsurface resistivity (Figure 12). In mineral exploration, ERT is particularly useful for detecting resistive or conductive anomalies associated with mineral deposits, such as sulfide zones, clay alteration, or quartz veins. The choice of electrode configuration and spacing can be optimized to target specific depths and resolution requirements. Its integration with other geophysical data (e.g., Induced Polarization or magnetic surveys) enhances its effectiveness in delineating mineralized zones (Martí et al., 2009; Dahlin & Zhou, 2004). Moreover, ERT provides a cost-effective, non-invasive alternative in areas where traditional drilling may be limited by terrain or access (Supper et al., 2009).

Figure 12: High level diagram process for ERT-IP.

In the PERSEPHONE project, ERT is applied, both in downhole and face-scanning configurations. The ABEM Terrameter LS is used as the resistivity meter. It records raw current and voltage readings across multiple electrode pairs, along with metadata such as electrode positions, timestamps, stacking settings, and measurement quality flags. More details about the configuration of the ERT within the PERSEPHONE project will be

found in D6.2 Design and validation of methods of analysis of structural properties of the orebody.

4.1.5.2 Data processing and calibration

Once acquisition is complete, raw data are typically stored in proprietary file formats (e.g., .DAT, .BIN, or .TXT) containing metadata such as electrode positions, timestamp, stacking information, and measurement quality.

The data transformation process involves several steps (Figure 15):

1. *Download and conversion:* Field data are downloaded to a computer and often converted to a standardized format (e.g., .dat, .csv) using software like ABEM's Terrameter LS Toolbox or RES2DINV.
2. *Preprocessing:* This includes filtering out bad readings, applying geometric factors, and correcting for contact resistance and topography.
3. *Formatting for broker integration:* Data are reformatted to meet the schema required by the data broker (Kafka). This typically includes tagging data with geolocation, timestamps, configuration details, and instrument identifiers.

Figure 13: Data transformation process for the ERT-IP sensor.

Whilst ERT equipment does not have a proper “calibration” process, several steps can and have to be made to ensure the data accuracy and interpretability. Several quality control and validation steps can be taken during the different acquisition phases (Table 2, Martí et al., 2009; Binley & Kemna, 2005, Dahlin & Zhou, 2004).

Table 2: Calibration process description for ERT and IP system

Calibration area	Calibration name	Description
------------------	------------------	-------------

Instrument calibration	Regular equipment checks	Test cables, electrodes, and the resistivity meter against known resistors to verify performance.
	Temperature compensation	Resistivity is temperature-dependent, environmental conditions (especially in shallow surveys) should be monitored and corrected if necessary.
Field calibration	Electrode contact test	Before data collection, ensure that each electrode has good ground contact. High contact resistance can lead to noisy or unusable data.
	Reciprocal measurement	For a given pair of current and potential electrodes, measure the voltage with current directions reversed. The difference between forward and reciprocal measurements helps identify bad data.
	Stacking and averaging	Multiple measurements are averaged to reduce noise from environmental and instrumental sources.
Inversion calibration	Use of synthetic model	Run synthetic forward models based on expected subsurface conditions to test inversion settings and sensitivity before field deployment
	Constraining inversion	Incorporate borehole data, known geological contacts, or topography to constrain and improve inversion results.
	Topographic corrections	Use terrain models to correct electrode elevations, as ignoring topography can distort the resistivity model.
Ground truthing and validation	Core drilling and boreholes	Compare ERT results with borehole logs to verify resistivity contrasts and refine geological interpretations.

	Laboratory resistivity measurements	Collect rock samples from the site and measure their resistivity under controlled conditions to relate lab values to field data.
	Integration with other methods	Combine ERT with other data (IP, seismic, magnetic, ...) for cross-validation of anomalies and structures.

Validation procedures are applied during acquisition to monitor instrument performance and environmental conditions. These quality assurance steps are the same for both downhole and face-scanning configurations, as defined in D1.2 “Requirements, specifications and benchmarking tools for proposed technologies.”

4.1.5.3 Data transmission

The cleaned and structured data are sent to the data broker via APIs, or file transfer protocols, for further processing, visualization, or digital twin integration. This transformation ensures the resistivity data are machine-readable, interoperable, and ready for downstream analysis and decision-making. A diagram explaining the process is presented in Figure 16.

Figure 14: Data transformation from .inv file to JSON. The metadata section can be expanded to include time log, instrument ID, inversion parameters and RMS error.

4.2 Integrated data processing and geomodelling workflow (Steps 3-7)

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Having described the sensor-specific data pipelines, we now turn to the integration of all data and the geological modelling process that uses this data. Steps 3 through 7 encompass taking the processed sensor outputs, merging them as needed, feeding them into the modelling software (Leapfrog in our case), generating a geological model and then exporting updates to the MineRP platform. This section is structured in subparts corresponding to the major integration and modelling steps:

- **Sensor data integration and broker system (Step 3–4):** how the data broker (Kafka) and any intermediate algorithms combine multi-sensor data and ensure it is ready for modelling. This includes handling site-specific calibration consolidation and preparing synthetic data streams.
- **Synthetic dataset generation protocol:** a recap of how we generated and used synthetic sensor data to simulate real sensor outputs (as a stand-in for Step 5 inputs).
- **Implicit geological modelling in Leapfrog (Step 6):** how Leapfrog Geo was configured to build the grade model from the incoming data, including constraints like boundaries and trends, and the process of continuous model update.
- **MineRP integration (Step 7):** how the resulting model (specifically the block model with grades) can be transmitted to the MineRP platform and how the temporal aspect (updates) is handled.

4.2.1 Sensor data integration and Kafka data broker (Steps 3–4)

After each sensor's data is pre-processed and transmitted to the Kafka broker (as described in 4.1), the integration framework must collect and organize these multi-source data streams for use in modelling.

4.2.1.1 High-frequency data streaming

Kafka provides a distributed, fault-tolerant log for streaming sensor data. Each sensor or device acts as a producer, publishing messages to Kafka topics categorized by equipment type, operation zone, or data class (e.g., air quality, geolocation, vibration). Consumers, such as spatial planning systems, alerting modules, or storage backends, subscribe to relevant topics to retrieve real-time or batched data streams.

This architecture allows for:

- High availability and scalability to support hundreds of concurrent sensors.
- Backpressure resistance, enabling consumers to process data at their own pace.
- Durability, ensuring that no data is lost even when consumers temporarily go offline.

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4.2.1.2 *Data contracts and schema evolution*

To manage the dynamic nature of sensor payloads, where new fields may be added or formats may change, Kafka integrates well with schema management tools like Confluent Schema Registry. This registry enforces data contracts, where producers must serialize messages according to Avro, Protobuf, or JSON schemas, and consumers deserialize data accordingly.

This ensures:

- **Forward and backward compatibility:** Older consumers can ignore unknown fields, and new consumers can handle extended payloads.
- **Schema validation at runtime:** Preventing malformed or non-compliant data from entering the pipeline.
- **Evolutionary data handling:** Allowing the seamless addition of new sensor data fields without breaking downstream systems.

4.2.1.3 *Maintaining data integrity*

Kafka's support for message ordering, immutability, and exactly-once semantics ensures the integrity of time-series data critical for spatial planning. By partitioning topics based on sensor IDs or mining zones, Kafka preserves temporal sequencing, a key requirement for correlating physical events underground with their spatial context.

Additionally, using Kafka Connect with built-in transformations and dead-letter queues helps capture transformation errors or unexpected schema violations, allowing operations teams to debug without disrupting production pipelines.

In summary, Steps 3–4 in our system are about preparing the data for modelling: ensuring all relevant sensor outputs are collected, time-aligned, spatially referenced, and possibly fused or computed into the forms needed by the modelling software. For now, it served to push data into Leapfrog in the correct format.

4.2.2 **Synthetic data generation protocol**

Once sensor data has been acquired, validated, and pre-processed through an intermediary data broker and corresponding signal-processing algorithms, it is transformed into geologically meaningful parameters such as elemental grades, mineralogical composition, and lithological classifications. These parameters are subsequently transmitted to a geological modelling software. For this project, Leapfrog Geo is employed due to its capability for implicit modelling and support for real-time server-based data integration and automatic model updates.

Due to the lack of live sensor feeds by the time of this deliverable, a synthetic dataset was developed to emulate outputs from a multispectral sensor configured

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to detect magnesite (MgCO_3) content. This approach allowed us to verify the end-to-end pipeline (from data capture to model update) and to illustrate results that are geologically plausible. This data simulation was based on laboratory-grade values provided by Grecian Magnesite and spatially distributed to match known patterns in their mine operations.

The magnesite content was derived from a mass-balance equation:

$$\text{MgCO}_3 = 100\% - (\text{SiO}_2 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{CaCO}_3)$$

where

$$\text{CaCO}_3 = \text{CaO} \times \frac{100}{56}$$

This approach assumes an inverse correlation between silica (SiO_2) and magnesite concentrations. The fictive dataset includes (X, Y, Z) spatial coordinates, simulating sensor sampling locations within the mine tunnel, and grade values based on Gaussian-distributed variations calibrated to laboratory values from Grecian Magnesite.

To simulate real-time data updates via the Kafka stream, a SQL script was used to insert new data into a linked SQL server connected to the Leapfrog model. This approach mimicked an active operational scenario where the model responded to incoming data. Snapshots were captured at intervals to observe how the model evolved with each update.

4.2.3 Implicit geological modelling with Leapfrog Geo (Step 6)

The construction of the geological model follows a hierarchical and iterative methodology utilizing Leapfrog's implicit modelling engine:

4.2.3.1 Lithological domain modelling

Lithological modelling begins with defining veins and host rock units based on legacy geological mapping. To enhance geological realism and control interpolation, several modelling constraints are introduced:

- *Hard boundaries*: enforced at lithological contacts, ensuring no data extrapolation occurs across units with distinct genesis (e.g., magnesite vs. ultramafic host).
- *Soft boundaries*: used within similar lithologies to allow grade continuity while respecting domain boundaries.
- *Structural trends*: a directional trend surface is defined to align modelling with vein geometry and structural fabric, typically constrained along a dominant azimuth and dip (e.g., NNE–SSW strike, 35° dip SE).

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These constraints influence the interpolation behaviour of the implicit functions used to model lithology and grade.

4.2.3.2 Grade model generation

Using the lithological framework, magnesite grades are interpolated across the domain using radial basis functions (RBF) or ordinary kriging (OK) as:

$$\hat{Z}(\mathbf{s}_0) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i Z(\mathbf{s}_i)$$

where

$\hat{Z}(\mathbf{s}_0)$ is the estimated grade at location \mathbf{s}_0 ,

$Z(\mathbf{s}_i)$ are the known values at sampling locations \mathbf{s}_i ,

λ_i are the weights determined by spatial correlation (variogram models).

4.2.3.3 Block model development

Once grade surfaces are defined, the volume is discretized into 3D blocks, with each block assigned lithological and grade attributes. The 3D block model is constructed with the following specifications:

- **Parent Block Size:**

$$X = 0.5 \text{ m}, \quad Y = 1.0 \text{ m}, \quad Z = 0.5 \text{ m}$$

- **Sub-blocking Strategy:**

Subdivision into $2 \times 2 \times 2$ sub-blocks to better capture geometries along contacts and thin vein structures.

- **Minimum Block Size:**

$$X_{\min} = 0.25 \text{ m}, \quad Y_{\min} = 0.5 \text{ m}, \quad Z_{\min} = 0.25 \text{ m}$$

This block model supports both categorical lithology and continuous grade attributes.

4.2.3.4 Model update and simulation workflow

The crucial test was updating the model when new data appears. To simulate this, we initially ran the interpolation with only a subset of the synthetic data (e.g., only 5% of the data). Then, we “released” more data (as if the robot moved further or drilled more). As new data points are fed incrementally, mimicking field-based sensor acquisition, the implicit model is regenerated. This includes both vein topology adjustments and grade re-interpolation, ensuring up-to-date geological representations. The output of this simulation modelling was a series of model

realizations (block models) reflecting the best estimate of grades given the sensor data up to that time.

Upon completion of the data input and grade population phase, the block model becomes finalized and ready for export into downstream applications, such as mine planning through MRP platform.

Figure 15: Model Update Simulation in Leapfrog Geo. The figure illustrates how block models are updated using new information, in this case magnesite %, as 'synthetic data' is generated. The example shown uses fictive multispectral input to simulate the update process.

4.2.4 MineRP Integration (Step 7)

The concluding step of the workflow is to make the updated geological model available to mine planning and other systems. In PERSEPHONE, the MineRP

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platform is used as the centralized environment for the digital twin geomodel, mine planning, and decision support. Therefore, once our Leapfrog model is regenerated with new sensor data, those changes need to propagate to the MineRP system. The geomodel in MineRP is as mentioned earlier developed in WP7.

5 Conclusions

The key conclusions drawn from the deliverable D2.4 are as follows:

1. Development of a data model

A functional and adaptable data model has been established to manage the flow of sensor data from raw acquisition to geological modelling. Kafka was set-up and utilized as the central data broker, to manage real-time streaming and transformation of diverse sensor inputs for integration into the digital twin and geomodel.

2. Sensor integration and calibration

Multiple sensing technologies, including MWD, multispectral imaging, LIBS, ultrasonic testing, and ERT, have been incorporated into the system architecture. Each sensor type is supported by specific calibration methods or reference tools to enhance data accuracy, standardization, and reliability under both laboratory and field conditions.

3. Use of simulated and synthetic data

Given the ongoing development and limited field availability of some sensors, synthetic and fictive datasets were generated to simulate real-world scenarios. These datasets enabled validation of the data pipeline and demonstrated the responsiveness of the geomodel to evolving inputs.

4. Capability for rock characterization

The integration of complementary sensor data allows for the continuous estimation of key rock properties, including hardness, mineral composition, strength, and structural features. This capability supports dynamic updating of the geomodel, providing a foundation for real-time interpretation and decision-making during underground operations.

5. Operational considerations

On the operational side, a number of considerations and challenges were identified. Sensor hardware must be ruggedized (for dust, shock, moisture – we have proposed solutions like protective housings and periodic maintenance/cleaning schedules). Power and data connectivity in the mine needs to be ensured – for instance, ensuring the rig or robot carrying these sensors has enough battery or using mine power where available, and having a network (likely wireless or a fiber tether) for data to reach the surface or control centre. Data format standardization is another area to continue working on so that integration with existing mine systems is smooth.

6. Challenges and next steps

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The project has identified several challenges, including the need for further refinement of calibration tools, handling data variability, and ensuring robust sensor performance in harsh mining environments.

The next step in the project related to this task is task 3.2 and that will focus on addressing these challenges, improving sensor integration, and enhancing the data model to support fully autonomous and sustainable mining operations. The next steps include deploying the sensor prototypes in a pilot site, collecting real data, and encountering new issues to solve (noise levels, data volume management, sensor failure modes, etc.).

In conclusion, the work done in D2.4 demonstrates a proof-of-concept integrated sensing system at TRL 3 and moves the mining industry closer to the vision of a fully autonomous, smart mine. The data infrastructure and modelling algorithms in simulated environment can be implemented once the sensor technologies mature (WP6) and are deployed. This integration of real-time data with modelling is a key enabler for the vision of autonomous, continuously optimizing mining systems and will in the next step D3.2 go to TRL 5.

The work done in this deliverable will feed into subsequent project tasks (notably WP3 Demonstrations and WP4 and WP5 Robotics integration) and provides a blueprint for the digital thread connecting raw sensor data to high-level mine planning decisions.

6 References

ERT

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MWD

M. Saadati, K. Weddfelt, P.-L. Larsson. (2020). A Spherical Indentation Study on the Mechanical Response of Selected Rocks in the Range from Very Hard to Soft with Particular Interest to Drilling Application.

7 Annex

The following annex provides detailed technical descriptions, data, and results for each sensor evaluated in Task 2.4.

7.1 MWD

During drilling with a drill rig a set of sensors are used to feedback information about different pressures etc. to the RCS-system be able to control the drilling performance and to measure if there are problems occurring and optimize the drilling. Also drill length is measured. These different pressure- and position data are also recorded and used as data to be able to read out the drilling performance and is called MWD (measure while drilling). The length sensor is also used to measure speed of the drilling, in MWD called penetration rate. Most pressures are set by the operator and can be seen as the input to the drilling system. One of the outputs is the penetration rate. That is used to get an understanding about the hardness of the rock.

MWD data helps in estimating rock hardness by analysing drilling parameters such as penetration rate, feed pressure, and rotation pressure. However, accurate measurement of rock hardness requires extensive data collection and calibration using additional methods like Schmidt hammer tests and geological surveys. The hardness scale is developed by comparing MWD data with geological information and adjusting for factors like previous blasting effects and collaring. To use a calibration tool to be able to get an absolute value of the rock during drilling is of great help to ensure proper rock characteristics data. In this project an indentation device described in the next chapter have been tested.

7.1.1 Indentation device used as calibration tool.

Today one of the software's using MWD to show hardness is Underground Manager (Epiroc), in that software hardness and fracturing is calculated to a relative value to show the user data how the hardness on the face is varying. It is set by the user as a grade between soft and hard with correlated colours. With a calibration tool like the indentation device, it is investigated if it can be used to transform the relative value into an absolute value (preferred UCS). The MWD data used to calculate the hardness value is penetration rate. The idea is to use the penetration rate as it is used today but also add the calibration value from the indentation device to get an absolute value via a method or script. That value will then be added to the MWD-data before it is sent to the data lake (Kafka).

To ensure a correct value as possible it is needed to make several indentations on the face/wall/roof.

7.1.2 Indentation device development, achievements

Background (from D1.2); An indentation device will be tested as a calibration tool for the MWD hardness data that today gives a relative value. The indentation device will give a calibration value to a method or software application that will result in a mechanical characterization value of the rock. The device is based on

indentation test in general and the current version is spherical indentation (closer to Brinell), but we are not limited to this shape of indenter. Below is a description of the development and testing of the indentation device before and during the Persephone project.

1. In the paper: “A Spherical Indentation Study on the Mechanical Response of Selected Rocks in the Range from Very Hard to Soft with Particular Interest to Drilling Application” (M. Saadati · K. Weddfelt · P.-L. Larsson 2020), indentation was used to investigate the mechanical response of different rock types. Focus was to investigate at what force an indentation depth does the rock break. One example of how the result can look is according to Figure 16. The diagram shows the force-penetration (F-d) response, it has two parts (a) up to the load capacity; (b) post-load capacity. The top part can be seen as the major brake of the rock, even if chipping occurs earlier in some cases. The curves look different for different rock types. For UCS, calculation’s part (a) can be used via back calculating and that part is what is investigated further in the Persephone project.

Figure 16: Graph and test results from indentation tests done in “A Spherical Indentation Study on the Mechanical Response of Selected Rocks in the Range from Very Hard to Soft with Particular Interest to Drilling Application”.

Figure 17: First version (left) of indentation equipment and the second version (right) mounted in portal which is used in the Persephone project.

- The indentation device was further developed with an internal length sensor and force sensor, see Figure 18. Measuring Technique lab at Epiroc conducted indentation tests on granite in the lab using this device, and the results were consistent with the previous findings.

Figure 18: Diagram showing force and indentation from version 2 of the indentation device. Both results from the portal and the indenter are shown. Portal values are used to verify the indenter.

- The third step was to perform indentation tests in the field with a surface drill rig. The purpose was to make a first field test to see the robustness and get values for UCS-calculation. Some minor updates were identified for

improvement. To extend the amount of sampling data CUPRUM have sent rock samples from KGHM mine for more testing of the indentation device.

Table 3: Result from field test of indentation test (red is unacceptable and orange is questionable test)

Rock type	Test no	UCS MPa (indent.)	Possible reason	UCS Mpa (lab data)
Granite-eyra	7	198		
Granite-eyra	8	203		
Granite-eyra	10	251		
Granite-eyra	11	147	no indentation but initial force	
Granite-eyra	12	354	vertical slope	
Granite-eyra	16	51	large sliding	
Granite-eyra	19	327	sliding+new contact area?	
Granite-eyra	20	221		
Granite-eyra	22	162	sliding	
Granite-eyra	23	192		
Granite-eyra	24	293	vertical slope	
Granite-eyra	25	162	small sliding	
Granite-eyra	28	158		
Granite-eyra	29	51	large sliding	

Figure 19: Photos from the field test conducted in December 2024 also photo of core sampling for UCS lab test from the same site.

4. Core samples were collected from the field near the locations where indentations had previously been made. These samples were sent for UCS testing to compare with the UCS values predicted from the field indentation method.

Table 4: Result from UCS-lab test

SPECIMEN	DIAMETER	HEIGHT	WEIGHT	HEIGH/DIA. RATIO	DENSITY	UCS	ANGLE OF FAILURE
No.	[mm]	[mm]	[g]		[kg/m ³]	[MPa]	[°]
4	55.70	139.05	869.28	2,50	2566	139.5	17
7.1	55.75	139.05	883.97	2,49	2604	175.3	18
7.2	55.57	128.21	808.05	2,31	2599	186.0	18
8	55.85	139.12	883.92	2,49	2594	153.4	20
10	55.84	139.12	885.38	2,49	2599	145.2	20

Figure 20: Eyra field test map.

5. The last step in this task involves comparison of indentation values vs UCS lab test. As shown in the Table 5, most UCS results were within 10–15% of the lab test values. However, greater deviation was observed for the indentation near hole number 10, likely due to the sample being taken further from the actual indentation point. Overall, the lab UCS results in this rock formation indicate significant variability depending on the exact location of sampling.

Table 5: Result from UCS lab test compared with the filed test results.

Rock type	Field test no.	Field UCS prediction MPa	Lab test sample no. (close to hole no.)	Rocklab UCS test MPa
Granite/Pegmatite	25	162	4	139.5

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Granite/Pegmatite	28	158	4	139.5
Granite/Pegmatite	8	203	7.1	175.3
Granite/Pegmatite	10	251	7.2	186
Granite/Pegmatite	-	-	8	153.4
Granite/Pegmatite	20	221	10	145.2
Granite/Pegmatite	22	162	10	145.2
Granite/Pegmatite	23	192	10	145.2

7.1.3 Indentation device: conclusions and next steps

Not all measurements could be used due to different reasons and the measurements that could be used were slightly “hit-or-miss” since calculations only could be done on some of the tests, due to the feed and boom system of the rig slipping slightly during load. While the methodology showed promising results and aligned with earlier lab tests, field deployment revealed areas needing improvement. To ensure consistent results, enhancements are required to address issues such as sliding and temperature sensitivity.

To further develop this device a new displacement transducer should be built that isn't as temperature sensitive and has a higher resolution. The indenter also must be more adapted to field tests, meaning that it's stable enough to not slip as often as the current prototype alternatively the product needs to indicate if it is a good or bad sample. Adaptations and more tests are needed, preferably on an underground drill rig.

Today in some mines or tunnelling projects mapping of rock hardness and calibration is done with a Schmidt hammer that is recorded for several faces to get a proper calibration value of the hardness and then relate that to the indication values set in the software Underground Manager.

This way of work would probably need to be used also when using the indentation device, at least until the indentation method has proved itself.

7.1.4 MWD data processing

All sensor signals are within the RCS-system transferred to corresponding values related to pressures, length etc. That data is for recording purpose created into an xml-file that can be downloaded as an MWD-file. Kafka can handle that kind of data, the transformation part is to add hardness data to the xml-file.

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The actual script or method to use the calibration value to transform the relative hardness value to absolute hardness value is still under development and needs to be concretized if the further testing shows that this is a way forward. The way it should work is described in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Process for calculating UCS from MWD-data, calculate directly from MWD data using penetration rate.

7.1.5 Challenges

One uncertainty is that during the start of the drilling process a lower percussion pressure is used to ensure a straight hole start. When the drill steel is around 0.4-0.8 m in the hole (can differ, a lot depending on rock quality etc.) it goes up to full percussion power. That means that the penetration rate is lower at the entrance which will give a fault value for the recalculation to hardness. That opens for several areas of investigation. One is to investigate adding percussion power in the relation indentation result and penetration rate and adapt the value accordingly. The other is to use this method to look backwards as shown in Figure 22. That means that calibration of the hardness in face 2 is correlated with the penetration rate from face 1.

Figure 22: Principal visualization of indentation device usage in forward calibration and backwards calibration.

7.2 Multispectral camera

7.2.1 Case study GM (aka abandoned mine): Magnesite purity classification

The SWIR camera collects images of exposed magnesite-rich rock on the mine wall. Each image is timestamped. The spectral range (900–1700 nm) covers known absorption bands of carbonates and silicates, enabling discrimination of magnesite (MgCO_3) from amorphous SiO_2 , dunite and serpentinite. Raw SWIR images are first radiometrically calibrated (subtract dark current, divide by pre-recorded images on white-reference panels) to convert to reflectance. Noise reduction (e.g. median or Gaussian filtering via NumPy/SciPy) and bad-pixel correction are applied. If the camera moves between shots, multi-frame registration or mosaic stitching aligns consecutive images. The result is a clean spectral image cube (in this case 2D spatial \times 8 spectral bands).

For each pixel or small region, we extract features that highlight magnesite versus silica, dunite and serpentinite. For example, magnesite and amorphous silica have different reflectance slopes and absorption peaks in SWIR, especially around 900nm and 1400nm. We can compute band ratios or feed selected bands into a classifier. In practice, a machine-learning model is trained on labelled SWIR spectra: random forest or logistic regression on known magnesite and gangue samples. Lab tests performed in Persephone WP6 show such classifiers can distinguish magnesite vs gangue with very high accuracy using SWIR features.

The processed image is turned into a binary mask of “magnesite-like” vs “non-magnesite” pixels. This can be done by thresholding the classifier’s probability or index value. We then find contiguous regions (chunks) of magnesite using connected-component labelling (e.g. `skimage.measure.label`). Each chunk is a candidate ore fragment. For each chunk we compute $\text{purity} = (\text{number of magnesite pixels}) / (\text{chunk area})$. Defined purity groups (1–4) correspond to thresholds, e.g. Group 1 = $\geq 99\%$ MgCO_3 , Group 4 = $< 85\%$. These thresholds can be adjusted based on the GM recommendations.

For each scan we generate a JSON record, for example:

```
{
  "timestamp": "2025-06-01T12:34:56Z",
  "chunks": [
    {"id":1, "purity_group":2, "magnesite_frac":0.76, "area_m2":0.5},
    {"id":2, "purity_group":1, "magnesite_frac":0.91, "area_m2":0.4}
  ]
}
```

This JSON includes the time and location of the image, and an array of chunk results (with assigned purity group and statistics). The robot edge publishes this JSON to Kafka.

7.2.2 KGHM deep mine case study: Copper content estimation in dolomite.

The SWIR camera captures images of the dolomite-rich rock (in our case, the stratigraphic layer below the Kupfer Schiefer layer. Consistency in lighting is ensured by keeping robot to mine face distance as constant as possible (calibration is made for a distance of 1.5m). Images undergo the same calibration (dark/white reference) and noise filtering steps as the abandoned mine case study. As the copper is disseminated, we process on a per-pixel or per-small-region basis, rather than isolating pure chunks.

Using collected reference samples from the face and measured their Cu% in the lab (SEM-EDS). For each reference point, we locate the corresponding region/pixels in the SWIR image and average their spectra. This pairs SWIR spectral signatures with true copper content. Typically, we reduce dimensionality (e.g. pick a few key bands or apply PCA) to avoid collinearity. Using the labelled spectral data (features) and Cu% (target), we train a regression model (python `scikit-learn`). A partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR), or nonlinear models like `RandomForestRegressor` is used to fit the data. We train and validate the model (e.g. k-fold cross-validation) on the sample data. Once trained, the model is stored on the edge computer.

The edge device applies the regression model to new image data. For the entire imaged region, it predicts Cu% for each pixel or block. For a chunk-based approach, contiguous dolomite areas are segmented (e.g. by thresholding a dolomite spectral index) and each chunk’s mean spectrum

is run through the model. The result is an estimated copper content (e.g. average Cu%) for that chunk.

The robot then formats the output, for example:

```
{
  "timestamp": "2025-06-01T12:35:00Z",
  "results": {"mean_Cu_pct": 0.23, "max_Cu_pct": 0.31}
}
```


Figure 23: Multispectral processing workflows for the two Persephone case studies.

7.2.3 Challenges

Mine tunnels subject hardware to dust, moisture and constant vibration. For industrial deployment the imager can be fitted with a protective quartz window kept clear by an air-knife and monitored by routine inspections. If Kafka is unreachable the edge computer simply queues JSON messages locally and re-sends them when the link comes back, ensuring data are never lost.

7.3 LIBS slurry

7.3.1 LIBS in short

The acronym LIBS is short for **L**aser **I**nduced **B**reakdown **S**pectroscopy and is a sensing technique that after decades of development has recently become commercially interesting in a multitude of applications due to advancements in

technology. The technique provides reliable data on the atomic composition of any type of sample, be it in solid, liquid or gaseous state.

Measurements are performed by shooting a pulsed, high-energy laser beam onto the surface of a sample. The laser ablates, or ‘evaporates’, a very small amount of material from the surface and forms a tiny, hot plasma which is visible as a spark. This plasma consists of atoms, ions and free electrons. As the plasma cools down, excited electrons fall back into their atomic or ionic orbits and release light at discrete energy levels. This light is collected by optics in the LIBS system and at the end of the chain measured by a spectrometer. and is characteristic for the composition of a sample at an atomic level.

Figure 24: Simplified overview of a basic LIBS system.

Figure 24 provides a simplified, schematic representation of the principle steps of any LIBS setup.

1. A laser shoots repetitive high-energy pulses onto a sample.
2. Using a set of optics, the laser pulses are focused onto the surface of the sample to create an extremely high energy density for a short amount of time.
3. The rapid influx of energy starts the ablation process, in which a tiny amount of sample material is transformed into a plasma.

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4. Light radiating from this plasma is collected by optics in the LIBS system and directed into a spectrometer. The spectrometer translates the light readings into a spectrum.
5. The recorded spectrum displays discrete energy spikes at specific wavelength positions. The positions of the energy spikes tells us which elements are detected within our sample, while the intensity of the peaks are related to the concentration of said elements.

LIBS is inherently a semi-quantitative analysis tool. The intensity of the emissions in the recorded spectra are related to their respective concentrations, but there are many other conditions (environmental, instrumentation) that can also affect this reading. That is why for any LIBS sensor to produce quantitative data, that system must first be calibrated. The required procedure for this is strongly dependent on the system in question, application and environmental conditions.

7.3.2 The use-case

For the Persephone project Spectral will be developing a very specialized LIBS system. It has been proposed to use LIBS to chemically analyse the drilling fluids created by a production drill-rig underground and in-situ. Underground drilling traditionally uses water to remove cut rock material from the drillhole, as well as to cool the drill bit. These drilling fluids containing the rock chips normally are not considered in the mining process and are left as they are.

This approach is different from what is conventional in most surface-level RC drilling. There it is often standard practice to collect drill chips and perform a series of analyses on them, which in turn is crucial information to any mining project. Due to the wet nature of underground drilling this is unfortunately not yet possible for underground mining with existing technology.

With a dedicated and specialized LIBS system, this gap could be filled. LIBS, as opposed to several other chemical analysis techniques, can work on liquid samples. A drill rig could be fitted with a drilling fluid collection system that routes collected drilling fluids to a LIBS system mounted on the drill rig. The LIBS system continuously analyses the fluids and gives information on the chemical composition of the rock that has been drilled by the rig. This will create a chemical depth profile of the drillhole, very similar as what would have been achieved if a drill core was extracted and scanned. Something popularly called 'coreless coring'.

The value proposition of this concept is multifold. First of all, it allows for continuous verification and updating of the digital mine model. In that sense it is an essential part of maintaining a digital twin for chemical information, as there are very limited ways of obtaining similar information without dedicated and costly coring.

Secondly, since the chemical information is collected during drilling and before blasting, it will be possible to use that knowledge for decision-making about the blasting process. When the geology behind the mine face is better understood, perhaps it can be decided to not develop a drift any further because an orebody stops. Or perhaps the direction of development can be adjusted. This can make the

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extraction process much more efficient and diminish the production of waste significantly.

This last point can be best illustrated by Figure 25. Here two potential geologies are presented that are identical on the mine face. However, they are very different behind to what is visible to the geologist. Case B in the figure would probably warrant different decision-making as compared to case A. Such a decision can only be made if chemical information was collected during the production drilling phase, in this case using LIBS.

Figure 25: Two hypothetical geological settings that are identical on the mine-face level, but very different behind it.

7.4 Acoustic

7.4.1 Data storage

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Storing ultrasonic test data in a relational database is essential for ensuring data integrity, traceability, and efficient data management. Given the complexity and variety of parameters involved, ranging from geological site details to specific measurement configurations, a structured approach allows users to organize, retrieve, and analyse information systematically.

The Site table (Figure 26) contains metadata related to each sampling location, including the site name, geographical coordinates, geological setting, and links to visual documentation such as photographs or 3D models. Each site can be associated with multiple Samples, which are described in the Sample table by attributes like lithology, physical dimensions, anisotropy characteristics, and orientation relative to testing direction. This defines a one-to-many relationship between *Site* and *Sample*.

Figure 26: Data model of ultrasonic measurement relational database.

The Measurements table records the results of ultrasonic tests, capturing whether the test was performed in the lab or field, the arrangement type (e.g., direct, semi-direct), the estimated path length, and the computed P-wave velocities (mean, minimum, and maximum). Each measurement is linked to a specific sample and site, resulting in a one-to-many relationship from *Sample* and *Site* to *Measurements*. Furthermore, each measurement refers to a specific Equipment configuration—described in the Equipment table—which includes the transducers and cables used during testing. This defines a one-to-one relationship between *Measurements* and *Equipment*, ensuring that each result is accurately tied to the exact setup used.

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Kafka can update or associate the relevant Site entry, especially if the robot moves to a new location or geological setting. In contrast, tables such as Sample and Equipment remain relatively static and are referenced more than updated, as they describe standardized components or infrequently changing configurations. This architecture enables scalable, robust tracking of dynamic measurement

7.5 ERT

7.5.1 ERT data integration

ERT data, more specifically inversion files (.inv), are produced by ERT inversion softwares like RES2DINV, ResIPy, BERT, pyGIMLi. For integration into a database or a Kafka-based system, this file can be transformed into a JSON structure.

The following JSON schema is a general representation on how the .inv file would be treated:

```
{
  "$schema": "https://json-schema.org/draft/2020-12/schema",
  "title": "ERT Inversion Data Schema",
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "survey_id": {
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Unique identifier for the ERT survey."
    },
    "project": {
      "type": "string",
      "description": "Project or campaign name."
    },
    "inversion_date": {
      "type": "string",
      "format": "date",
      "description": "Date of inversion (YYYY-MM-DD)."
    },
    "electrode_spacing_m": {
      "type": "number",
      "description": "Spacing between electrodes in meters."
    },
    "model_units": {
      "type": "string",
      "enum": ["ohm-m"],
      "description": "Units of resistivity values."
    },
    "model_blocks": {
```

```

    "type": "array",
    "items": {
      "type": "object",
      "properties": {
        "x_m": { "type": "number", "description": "Horizontal position in meters." },
        "z_m": { "type": "number", "description": "Depth position in meters." },
        "resistivity": { "type": "number", "description": "Inverted resistivity value
(ohm-m)."} }
      },
      "required": ["x_m", "z_m", "resistivity"]
    }
  },
  "metadata": {
    "type": "object",
    "properties": {
      "software": { "type": "string" },
      "instrument_id": { "type": "string" },
      "operator": { "type": "string" },
      "location": { "type": "string" },
      "timelog": {
        "type": "object",
        "properties": {
          "start_time": { "type": "string", "format": "date-time" },
          "end_time": { "type": "string", "format": "date-time" }
        },
        "required": ["start_time", "end_time"]
      },
      "inversion_parameters": {
        "type": "object",
        "properties": {
          "max_iterations": { "type": "integer" },
          "regularization": { "type": "string" },
          "convergence_threshold": { "type": "number" },
          "depth_of_investigation_m": { "type": "number" }
        },
        "required": ["max_iterations", "regularization"]
      },
      "rms_error_percent": { "type": "number" },
      "notes": { "type": "string" }
    },
    "required": ["software", "instrument_id", "operator", "timelog",
"inversion_parameters"]
  }
},
"required": ["survey_id", "project", "inversion_date", "electrode_spacing_m",
"model_units", "model_blocks", "metadata"]

```

}

7.6 Kafka as a data broker technology

Kafka is used as a high-throughput, low-latency data broker that enables real-time data streaming between systems. It acts as a central messaging backbone, decoupling data producers (e.g., sensors, applications, services) from data consumers (e.g., analytics engines, databases, microservices).

Producers write data to Kafka topics, and consumers read from these topics independently and asynchronously. Kafka ensures durability, scalability, and fault tolerance, making it ideal for systems where data must flow reliably and efficiently across distributed components.

7.6.1 Data contracts and schema registry

The Schema Registry in Kafka serves as a data contract between producers and consumers by enforcing a consistent data structure. Producers serialize messages (typically using formats like Avro, Protobuf, or JSON Schema) before publishing them to a Kafka topic. These schemas are registered in the Schema Registry, which stores and versions them centrally. Consumers retrieve the schema (using an ID embedded in the message) to correctly deserialize and interpret the data.

This contract ensures that new schema versions can evolve while preserving backward or forward compatibility. It performs validation to ensure that invalid or malformed data is rejected before being published. Producers and consumers can evolve independently as long as they respect the agreed schema evolution rules.

7.6.2 Proof of concept

The following provides a demonstration of how MWD is uploaded to Kafka via a producer interface, how it is persisted in Kafka, and how a consumer application is notified whenever new data arrives under a specific topic. In the D2.4 data model it represents the stage 2 to either 3, 5 or 7.

The following is a screenshot of a MWD file in XML format (Figure 27).


```

<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<DRMWD IRVersion="V 1.2AC" IRDownCompat="V 1.2" DRMWDVersion="V 1.2AC" DRMWDDownCompat="V 1.2" xmlns="http://www.iredes.org/xml/DrillRig" xmlns:IR:
<IR:GenHead>
  <IR:FileCreateDate>2024-10-02T10:24:31</IR:FileCreateDate>
  <IR:IRVersion DownCompat="V 1.2">V 1.2AC</IR:IRVersion>
  <IR:ProjectInfo>
    <IR:Signature />
    <IR:Comment />
  </IR:ProjectInfo>
  <IR:EquipmentInfo>
    <IR:EqpManuFact>Epiroc</IR:EqpManuFact>
    <IR:EqpType>Boomer</IR:EqpType>
    <IR:EqpModel />
    <IR:EqpSerNo>999927300</IR:EqpSerNo>
    <IR:EqpSysVer>RCS 4.8</IR:EqpSysVer>
    <IR:EqpInfo />
    <IR:EqpName />
  </IR:EquipmentInfo>
</IR:GenHead>
<IR:ReportId>84178.093</IR:ReportId>
<IR:StartLogTime>2013-01-30T08:07:43</IR:StartLogTime>
<IR:EndLogTime>2013-01-30T08:09:19</IR:EndLogTime>
<MWDholeId>101</MWDholeId>
<PositionQuality>
<CoordSystem>
  <IR:CoordSysName />
  <IR:TMatrix>
    <IR:Col>
      <IR:x>0.111</IR:x>
      <IR:y>0.994</IR:y>
      <IR:z>0.000</IR:z>
      <IR:w>0.000</IR:w>
    </IR:Col>
    <IR:Col>
      <IR:x>0.994</IR:x>
      <IR:y>-0.111</IR:y>
      <IR:z>-0.004</IR:z>
      <IR:w>0.000</IR:w>
    </IR:Col>
    <IR:Col>
      <IR:x>0.004</IR:x>
      <IR:y>0.000</IR:y>
      <IR:z>1.000</IR:z>
      <IR:w>0.000</IR:w>
    </IR:Col>
  </IR:TMatrix>
</CoordSystem>
  </PositionQuality>
</MWDholeId>
</IR:ReportId>
</IR:EndLogTime>
</IR:StartLogTime>
</IR:GenHead>
</DRMWD>
  
```

Figure 27: screenshot of a MWD file in XML format.

Before this file can be uploaded to Kafka via a producer program, a schema registry entry has to be created to define the required data contract.

Schema Registry / BrokerDemo.HirogavaSample.Json-value

Actual version

```

{
  "$schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-04/schema#",
  "title": "HirogavaSample",
  "type": "object",
  "additionalProperties": false,
  "properties": {
    "LengthTag": {
      "type": "number",
      "format": "double"
    },
    "TimeTag": {
      "type": "string"
    },
    "FeedPressure": {
      "type": "number",
      "format": "double"
    },
    "DampeningPressure": {
      "type": "number",
      "format": "double"
    },
    "RotationSpeed": {
      "type": "number",
      "format": "double"
    },
    "RotationPressure": {
      "type": "number",
      "format": "double"
    }
  }
}
  
```

Version	ID	Type
3	5	JSON

Latest version: 3
 ID: 5
 Type: JSON
 Subject: BrokerDemo.HirogavaSample.Json-value
 Compatibility: BACKWARD

Figure 28: Schema registry in Kafka (example).

With a schema in place a producer program can now be used to upload the file to a specific topic on Kafka. The screenshot below is of the Kafka user interface where messages under a specific topic can be inspected (Figure 28).

Figure 29: Kafka user interface.

As the WDM file is being uploaded by the producer application, a notification is sent to a consumer application indicating a new record of the WDM file is available for download from the Kafka server (Figure 30).

Figure 30: Example of WMD file available for download in Kafka.

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7.7 Connections with other WPs.

The schematic below shows how the D2.4 data model is connected in more detail with the other WP.s in the Persephone project.

Figure 31: Relationship of D2.4 data model with other WPs within PERSEPHONE.